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HEALTHCARE SERVICES LOCATOR WITH WEB MAPPING AND CHATBOT UTILIZING THE HAVERSINE DISTANCE METRICS ALGORITHM

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Abstract

In this study, the Haversine formula was applied in the development of an Android-based application to measure the distance between the user's current location and healthcare facilities, utilizing a global positioning system (GPS) and the Java programming language to integrate the mobile application. The ChatGPT API was also utilized for the Chatbot, a feature of the application that allows users to ask questions related to health. A test was conducted by comparing the results of the Haversine and Vincenty formulas. A relative error formula was also used to evaluate the accuracy of the three nearest healthcare facilities. The three relative error results got the total average of 2.87%, which is considered a low relative error percentage. Based on the results of the relative error, the result was accurate, and made the application reliable for searching the nearest healthcare facilities within the barangay of District 2, Quezon City, Philippines.

Keywords:

Google Maps, Haversine Distance Formula, Healthcare Facilities, Hybrid Chatbot

1. INTRODUCTION

Accidents are one of the unavoidable things that can happen to an individual in their daily life, and when these things occur, knowing where to go and who to call for immediate aid is among the most important things that need to be known. Healthcare facilities play an important role in the community as facilities that offer individuals critical services. These services include proper medication, check-ups, tests, laboratory services, surgeries, and any other medical practices. Hospitals and clinics also employ doctors from various specialties, including family medicine, otolaryngology, dermatology, obstetrics and neurology, radiology, and cardiology.

People are unaware of the nearest health facilities within the vicinity, which can cause problems, especially during emergencies and unexpected circumstances.

Due to unawareness, more issues may arise, such as the worsening of the problem, and sometimes it can lead to a serious illness. Because of panic attacks, people tend to make bad decisions and choose the wrong healthcare facility to ask for help, and lastly, searching for the nearest hospital or clinic is time-consuming and energy-draining.

Objectives of the Study

The study aimed to develop an Android-based mobile application that is easy to use, responsive, and capable of providing accurate output based on the user's needs to help the users locate the nearest healthcare facilities in their areas. This would help the users avoid time-wasting and energy-draining searches for a healthcare facility that can offer the services needed in times of emergency.

The specific objectives are the following:

1. To develop the application using Android Studio.

2. To apply the Haversine formula in measuring the distance between the user's location and healthcare facilities.
3. To compare the calculated distances between points with Vincenty formula and determine the relative error.
4. To integrate a web mapping platform for displaying locations and providing direction to healthcare facilities.
5. To test and evaluate the application with ISO/IEC 25010 quality standards.

Scope and Delimitation

The Android-Based application is capable of locating and tracking the top three most accessible hospitals or clinics from user's location during emergencies within the areas of the Second District of Quezon City. Specifically in the barangays of Bagong Silangan, Batasan Hills, Commonwealth, Payatas, and Holy Spirit. It is equipped with a hybrid Chabot with a ChatGPT API. Gupta et al. (2020), mentioned that a Chatbot is a software application that functions between a human and a robot helper.

Further, it can only provide information of the facilities such as names, complete address, servicing hours and accurate distance. It does not give any medical advises and diagnosis to the users, The Chabot feature can only answer health related concern and lastly, this application can only be installed in an Android mobile device.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Global Positioning System (GPS)

Michael et al. (2006) said that GPS uses a process of triangulation in which you can find any position, and it measure the position, velocity, as well as time.

According to Uddin et al. (2013), the GPS system is already in place, and anyone can use it with no restrictions.

As discussed by Isa et al. (2019), the global positioning system is useful for a variety of matters. A satellite navigation and positioning system called GPS can offer time and location information without thinking about time or the environment anywhere in the world.

2.2. Google Map

Putra et al. (2018) explained, Google Maps has some options for viewing in original two-dimensional or three-dimensional views with 360 degrees panoramic images.

Mehta et al. (2019) discussed, Google Map is an innovation in the history of technology. With Google Map, people can travel the shortest route to their desired destinations.

2.3. Haversine Distance Formula

Hartanto et al. (2018) clarified that the Haversine formula is working when it comes to calculating the distance between locations by using latitude and longitude as inputs that can be used to perform a search.

Based on the study by Syaripudin et al. (2021), they were able to find the nearest school they were looking for based on the zoning system. However there are some inaccuracy due to the global positioning system.

2.4. Healthcare Facilities

Daskin et al. (2004) highlighted that applying facility location modelling to healthcare facilities gives it even more significance.

2.5. Locator Applications

As discussed by Rao et al. (2003), geography is crucial in determining the kind and nature of human beings' activities. Consumer information needs and product and service preferences may be influenced by location.

According to Amit Kushwaha and Vineet Kushwaha (2011), wireless gadgets that are location-aware allow users to ask questions about their surroundings at any time.

3. METHODOLOGY

The researchers employed the applied research in developing the prototype, quantitative, descriptive, and purposive sampling methods in collecting analysing, statistical treatment of data, utilizing distance metrics algorithms, and compare relative error.

3.1. Software Development Components

Table 1. Software Development Components

Component	Description
Android Studio	Created especially for Android development, as an integrated development environment for Google's Android operating system.
JAVA JDK	Oracle Corporation distributes Java Technology through the Java Development Kit. It offers the Java Application Programming Interface (API) Standard Edition and implements the Java language and Java Virtual Machine specifications.
SQLite	An open source relational database management engine written in C. It is used for back-end management and administration.

Google Map	A consumer app and online mapping platform provided by Google. It provides an alternative navigational route for traveling.
Global Positioning System (GPS)	An endeavor by the World Wide Web Consortium to create a uniform interface for retrieving a device's geographic location data.
ChatGPT	An API used to generate responses in the Chabot feature of the develop application.

Table 1 enumerates the software development components.

3.2. Software Development and Analytical Tools

Figure 1. Android Development Life

Figure 1 illustrates the life cycle of Android development, and it shows the steps on how to develop the application.

Figure 2. Conceptual Model

Figure 2 describes the conceptual model to characterize the structures, behaviors, and views of the application.

Figure 3. Block Diagram

Figure 3 displays the block diagram of the system that the user can see from their point of view. It provides information about the functions in the backend used in developing the application.

3.3. Screenshots of the Interface

Figure 4. Splash Page, Terms and Conditions, and Privacy Policy windows

Figure 5. Choosing Specialized Doctor and Google Map windows

Figure 6. The ChatBot Window

Figures 4, 5, and 6 were the actual screen shots of the interfaces of the android applications.

3.4. Relative Error Formula

By using this formula, it can estimate the absolute error's size in terms of the measurement's true size as shown in equation 1.

$$RE_{\text{accuracy}} = (\text{Absolute error} / \text{True value}) * 100\%$$

3.5. The Haversine Algorithm

This method determine the great-circle distance between two points on a sphere using latitude and longitude. This technique is applied to geospatial information systems applications. (Alam et al., 2016).

It was applied to measure the shortest distance between users' locations and the nearest healthcare facilities as shown in equation 2.

$$\begin{aligned} a &= \sin^2(\Delta\text{lat}/2) + \cos(\text{lat}1)\cos(\text{lat}2)\sin^2(\Delta\text{long}/2) \\ c &= 2\text{atan}2(\sqrt{a}, \sqrt{1-a}) \\ d &= R.c \end{aligned}$$

Where:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta\text{lat} &= \text{lat}2 - \text{lat}1 \\ \Delta\text{long} &= \text{long}2 - \text{long}1 \\ R &= \text{Earth's radius at } 6371 \text{ km} \\ c &= \text{axis intersection calculation} \\ d &= \text{distance in km} \end{aligned}$$

3.6. The Vincenty Formula

It was used to compare the results of the calculated shortest distance. According to Mahmoud et al. (2016), the Vincenty formula measures the geodesic distance, which is the shortest distance between two points on an ellipsoid and solves two geodesic problems: the direct problem and the inverse problem as shown in equation 3.

$vincenty_distance(lat1, lon1, lat2, lon2)$

3.7. Statistical Treatment of Data

In this part of the study, researchers list down all the tools and methods that were used to interpret the gathered data from thirty (30) respondents.

A rating scale, as shown on Table 2 was used to measure the responses collected from the respondents with corresponding verbal interpretation and range.

Table 2. Four-Point Likert Rating Scale

Verbal Interpretation	Range
Excellent	3.51 – 4.00
Very Good	2.51 – 3.50
Good	1.51 – 2.50
Poor	1.00 – 1.50

Frequency is the number of responses in a particular question. The formula of how to get the frequency as shown in equation 4.

Relative Frequency = f/N

Where:

Σ = Summation

f = Represents the frequency of a category

$N = \Sigma f$ = Represents the total population size

Percentage is used to determine and measure the number of responses over the number of respondents as shown in equation 5.

$P = f/n$

Where:

P = Represents as percentage

f = Frequency of each rating scale

n = Number of respondents

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The average weighted mean was used to calculate the overall results and represents the average of the collected data.

$$\text{Weighted Average} = (\sum wx) / (\sum w)$$

Where:

w = Weight for each data point
x = Value of each data point

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 3. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of Gender

Gender	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Female	16	53
Male	14	47
Total Population (N)	30	100

Table 3 indicates that majority of the respondents are female.

Table 4. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of Age

Age Bracket	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
26-33	10	33
34-49	9	30
16-25	8	27
50-Above	3	10
Total Population (N)	30	100

Table 4 shows that majority of the respondents are from the age bracket between 16 and 49.

Table 5. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of Living Status

Living Status	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Homeowner	15	50
Renter	15	50
Lessee/Landlord	0	0%
Total Population (N)	30	100

Table 5 explains the equal number of respondents who are homeowners and renters.

Table 6. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of Barangays

Barangay	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Holy Spirit	10	34%
Commonwealth	10	33%
Batasan Hills	10	33%
Total Population (N)	30	100

Table 6 presents the equal number of respondents in three barangays.

4.2. Pilot Testing Phase

Table 7. The distance between user's location and the facilities using the Haversine Formula

User's Location	Facilities	Calculated Distance
14.687010,121.086062	14.686368962632397,121.08561600879102	84.1 m
14.687010,121.086062	14.686448403310061,121.08475205908664	150.8 m
14.687010,121.086062	14.6867350707524, 121.08465161244709	151.2 m

Table 7 displays the distance of the top three nearest dental clinic facilities from the location of the user in Barangay Holy Spirit, Quezon City. The first facility, JDL Alvarez Dental Clinic, is located 84.1 meters away, which is the most accessible and nearest to the user. The next facility, Turbolencia Dental Clinic, is 150.8 meters away, and the third facility, Dr. Jennifer Alvarez Dental Clinic, is 151.2 meters away. The facilities are located at BF Homes Road, Holy Spirit.

Table 8. The distance between user's location and the facilities using the Vincenty Formula

User's Location	Facilities	Calculated Distance
14.687010,121.086062	14.686368962632397,121.08561600879102	85.7 m
14.687010,121.086062	14.686448403310061,121.08475205908664	154.2 m
14.687010,121.086062	14.6867350707524, 121.08465161244709	154.9 m

Table 8 enumerates the distance between users' locations and the top three nearest healthcare facilities using the Vincenty formula. The online Vincenty Formula calculator was used to calculate the longitudes and latitudes located at <https://www.gpsvisualizer.com/calculators>. It shows that the distance between the user and the first facility was 85.7 m, the second was 154.2 m, and the last was 154.9 m.

4.3. Experimental Results

Table 9. Relative Errors

Facilities	Calculated Distance by the application	Calculated Distance by Vincenty Formula	Absolute Error	Relative Error %
JDL Alvarez Dental Clinic	84.1 m	85.7	1.6	1.87%
Turbolencia Dental Clinic	150.8 m	154.2	3.4	2.2%
Dr. Jennifer Alvarez Dental Clinic	151.2 m	154.9	3.7	2.39%

Table 9 shows the measurements made by the developed application and by Vincenty formula which shows the absolute errors and relative errors.

The researchers used the calculated results using the Vincenty formula as the true value, and the calculated distance used the application as the measured value. The first facility shows 1.6 results of absolute error and 1.87% relative error; the second facility has an absolute error of 3.4 and 2.2% relative error results. While the third facility has 3.7 absolute errors and a relative error of 2.39%.

The average of the relative error results is 2.87%, considering the results of the relative error, both the Vincenty and the Haversine formulas were relatively close to each other, and because of this, the application can be considered a reliable one for searching for the top three nearest healthcare facilities in District 2, Quezon City.

Table 10. ISO/IEC 250 Quality Standards Evaluation Results

Criteria	Average Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Accessibility	3.0	Very Good
Maintainability	2.28	Good
Functionality	2.96	Very Good
Reliability	3.2	Very Good
Portability	2.88	Very Good
Usability	3.27	Very Good
Security	3.48	Very Good
Overall	2.87	Very Good

Table 10 explains the different criteria, the average weighted mean, and the corresponding verbal interpretation. As shown, the criteria on accessibility, obtained an average of 3.0 and was interpreted as "Very Good"; subsequently maintainability achieved 2.28 and was interpreted as "Good"; functionality attained 2.96 and was interpreted as "Very Good"; reliability gained 3.2 and was interpreted as "Very Good"; portability garnered 2.88% and was interpreted as "Very Good"; usability acquired 3.27 and was interpreted as "Very Good; and security got 3.48 and was interpreted as "Very Good." Overall, healthcare facility locators attained the overall mean average of 2.87 and was interpreted as "Very Good."

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, the researchers were able to design and develop an android-based healthcare facility locator for users in the second district of Quezon City. The application can measure the shortest distance between two points, and showed the top three closest facilities based on users' locations in an intuitive and practical manner.

The application can effectively be used by users who want to find the closest and most accessible facilities based on the medical services or doctors they require.

The following recommendations are hereby offered:

1. Use the Distance Matrix API for more accurate distance calculations because it calculates the actual groundwork.
2. Provide more data on healthcare facilities and add more medical services for the users to choose from.
3. The application covered only the area of District 2 of Quezon City, so it's advisable to expand the covered area further for it to be more useful and beneficial.
4. Integrate direction inside the map application to be more convenient for the user.

Conflict of Interest

The collaborative effort has no conflicts of interest among the researchers.

Informed Consent

The full consent of all respondents who took part in the conduct of this study was obtained.

Research Funding

All the expenses in the conduct of the study were collaboratively shared among the researchers.

Ethics Approval

The Research Ethics Board of the universities involved has duly approved this study after it undergone compliance with the locally and internationally accepted ethical guidelines.

REFERENCES

- Alam, C. N., Manaf, K., Atmadja, A. R., & Aurum, D. K. (2016). Implementation of haversine formula for counting event visitor in the radius based on Android application. 2016 4th International Conference on Cyber and IT Service Management (pp. 1-6). *IEEE*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CITSM.2016.7577575>
- Daskin, M.S., Dean, L.K. (2005). Location of Health Care Facilities. In: Brandeau, M.L., Sainfort, F., Pierskalla, W.P. (eds) *Operations Research and Health Care*. International Series in Operations Research & Management Science, vol 70. Springer, Boston, MA. https://doi.org/10.1007/1-4020-8066-2_3
- Gupta, A., Hathwar, D., & Vijayakumar, A. (2020). Introduction to AI chatbots. *International Journal of Engineering Research and Technology*, 9 (7), 255-258. <http://dx.doi.org/10.17577/IJERTV9IS070143>
- Isa, M. Z. M., Jamil, M. M. A., Ibrahim, T. N. T., Ahmad, M. S., Abd Rahman, N. A., & Adon, M. N. (2019, November). Children security and tracking system using Bluetooth and gps technology. In 2019 9th IEEE International Conference on Control System, Computing and Engineering (ICCSCE) (pp. 184-187). *IEEE*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCSCE47578.2019.9068542>
- Kushwaha, A., & Kushwaha, V. (2011). Location based services using android mobile operating system. *International Journal of Advances in Engineering & Technology*, 1(1), 14-20. <https://www.ijaet.org/media/Location-Based-Services-using-Android-mobile-Operating-System-Copyright-IJAET.pdf>
- Mahmoud, H., & Akkari, N. (2016). Shortest path calculation: A comparative study for location-based recommender system. World Symposium on Computer Applications & Research (WSCAR) (pp. 1-5). *IEEE*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/WSCAR.2016.16>
- Mehta, H., Kanani, P., & Lande, P. (2019). Google Maps. *International Journal of Computer Applications*, 178(8), 41-46. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-825x.2013.04878.x>
- Michael, K., McNamee, A., & Michael, M. G. (2006). The emerging ethics of humancentric GPS tracking and monitoring. *International Conference on Mobile Business* (pp. 34-34). *IEEE*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICMB.2006.43>
- Putra, I. K. G. D., Putra, I. M. S., & Putri, D. P. S. (2018). A Web-Based Geographic Information System for the Health Care Center Distribution in Bali https://simdos.unud.ac.id/uploads/file_penelitian_1_dir/Oba87378ce656244cc42a2fcb5699198.pdf

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- Rao, B., & Minakakis, L. (2003). Evolution of mobile location-based services. *Communications of the ACM*, 46(12), pp. 61-65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtte.2016.11.001>
- Syaripudin, U., Fauzi, N., Uriawan, W., Wildan, Z., & Rahman, A. (2021). Haversine Formula Implementation to Determine Bandung City School Zoning Using Android Based Location Based Service. In Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on Islam, Science and Technology, ICONISTECH 2019, 11-12 July 2019, Bandung, Indonesia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4108/eai.11-7-2019.2303558>
- Uddin, M. P., Islam, M. Z., Nadim, M., & Afjal, M. I. (2013). GPS-based Location Tracking System via Android device. *International Journal of Research in Computer Engineering and Electronics*, 2(5). https://www.researchgate.net/publication/259581222_GPS-based_Location_Tracking_System_via_Android_Device

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